

Comparative Analysis of AI Model and Optimisation Algorithms for Solving Inverse Kinematics in a 7-DOF Robotic System

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Abstract - This research provides a comparative analysis between artificial intelligence (AI) and optimization methods for solving inverse kinematics in a 7-DOF robotic system. It explores Differential Evolution, PSO, Simulated Annealing, Genetic Algorithm, Gradient Descent, Linear Regression Model, Decision Tree, Neural Network and Support Vector machine. The findings offer insights for selecting the most suitable method to address inverse kinematics challenges in diverse robotic applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The inverse kinematics problem is the fundamental of robotics, crucial for determining joint configurations to achieve desired end-effector positions and orientations, especially in complex 7-degree-of-freedom (7-DOF) systems. Traditional analytical methods struggle with the complexity and nonlinearity of such systems, necessitating alternative techniques. Artificial intelligence (AI) and optimization algorithms have emerged as promising solutions, offering robust methods to iteratively refine joint configurations for precise alignment of the end-effector. By leveraging the computational power and flexibility of AI and optimization, engineers can overcome the challenges of high-dimensional robotic designs. This study compares AI and optimization techniques for solving inverse kinematics in 7-DOF systems, provide insights into selecting the most suitable method to overcome inverse kinematics. Such research contributes to the advancement of robotics by promoting efficient and effective inverse kinematics solutions.

Overview of Kinematics

Kinematics refers to the study of robotic systems' mechanical behavior, focusing on their movement and operation within their surroundings. It involves comprehending the motion, positioning, and constraints imposed by their mechanical structure. Additionally, it delves into understanding the spatial arrangement of objects and their motion over time, playing a significant role in defining the position, velocity, and acceleration of robotic systems.

Forward Kinematics: is the process of calculating the precise position and orientation of the end-effector based on given joint configurations, employing geometric transformations like rotations and translations. Homogeneous

transformation matrices describe this mathematically, enabling the transmission of motion from the robot's base to its end-effector through coordinate transformations. It's crucial for tasks such as motion planning and trajectory generation.

Inverse Kinematics: is refers to the use of kinematic equations to determine robot movement to achieve a desired location. It's more challenging than forward kinematics due to solving nonlinear equations, vital for tasks like pick-and-place operations and obstacle avoidance. However, addressing inverse kinematics issues analytically, particularly in 7-degree-of-freedom (7-DOF) robotic systems, poses significant challenges, necessitating the exploration of new techniques such as artificial intelligence (AI) and optimization approaches.

Numerical approaches and optimization algorithms are typically employed to solve inverse kinematics issues, refining joint configurations to minimize error between desired and actual end-effector positions. By addressing inverse kinematics, engineers can precisely control robotic motion and execute tasks with precision and efficiency.

II. Literature Review

The complexity of solving inverse kinematics for manipulators with 7 degrees of freedom (DOF) arises from the additional degree of freedom compared to traditional systems. This additional DOF leads in an endless number of alternative solutions for a given end-effector location. Numerous research endeavours have investigated diverse methodologies aimed at tackling this challenge:

Ricardo Xavier da Silva et al. (2021) address the inverse kinematics challenge of a 7-degree-of-freedom serial redundant manipulator, which offers infinite solutions due to its additional degree of freedom. They employ Grobner bases theory, a method capable of resolving all solutions to polynomial equations, and the Denavit Hartenberg model for standardizing reference coordinate systems. Their study proposes a Grobner bases-based approach to efficiently solve the inverse kinematics issue, demonstrated on a KUKA LBR iiwa 7 R800 manipulator and validated through algebraic computing software. Future work may expand this method to other redundant manipulator types, incorporating factors like

obstacle avoidance and singularity resolution for enhanced performance.

Shimizu et al. (2008) tackle the analytical computation challenge of inverse kinematics for 7-DOF redundant manipulators with position domain joint limits. Their study introduces a parameterization method utilizing arm angles to derive closed-form solutions. They also develop a technique to identify feasible arm angles within joint limits and propose a redundancy resolution method via cost function optimization. Demonstrating the effectiveness of these methods in obtaining feasible inverse solutions across the global configuration space and addressing redundancy, the research validates its findings through kinematic simulations. Future enhancements could involve extending the methods to various redundant manipulators, considering dynamic characteristics, and comparing performance against existing approaches.

Hsu-Chih H. et al. (2012) tackle the computationally intensive inverse kinematics problem for 7-DOF robotic manipulators, which lacks general closed-form solutions. They propose a particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm to efficiently solve the redundant inverse kinematics problem by enabling intelligent cooperation between particles. Simulation results showcase the effectiveness of the PSO algorithm in identifying optimal configurations for the robotic manipulator, highlighting its potential for real-time robotics applications. This approach offers promise in addressing the complexity of inverse kinematics while paving the way for practical implementation in various robotic systems requiring efficient and adaptable motion planning strategies.

Huang et al. (2012) confront the challenge of redundant inverse kinematics in 7-DOF robotic manipulators, which lack general closed-form solutions vital for control and trajectory planning. They introduce a particle swarm optimization algorithm (PSO) to efficiently address the problem. The PSO algorithm minimizes a fitness function combining position error and joint angle displacement from the initial position. Simulation results demonstrate success in finding optimal joint angles for a given end-effector position, confirming convergence and effectiveness. Future opportunities include extending the PSO algorithm to incorporate additional constraints like joint limits, obstacle avoidance, and singularity avoidance, as well as comparing its performance with other metaheuristic algorithms for inverse kinematics problem-solving.

Li et al. (2022) focus on the constrained motion planning challenge of a 7-DOF free-floating space manipulator, requiring precise alignment of the end-effector position and orientation with the target. Their paper introduces a novel approach that merges deep reinforcement learning with artificial potential fields to boost the robustness and convergence of the planning algorithm. Through comparative

simulations, the study demonstrates the efficacy of this approach in achieving planning objectives while avoiding self-collision and minimizing base disturbance. Future endeavors could involve exploring more complex scenarios with multiple obstacles, dynamic targets, and uncertain disturbances to further validate the effectiveness and applicability of the proposed approach.

Sariyildiz et al. (2012) tackle the challenging inverse kinematic problem of a 7-DOF redundant robot arm, complicated by complexity and singularity issues. They employ two intelligent identification methods, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Support Vector Regression (SVR), to model the inverse differential kinematics. Simulation results reveal SVR's superiority over ANN in terms of modeling accuracy and generalization ability, attributed to its ability to avoid local minima and its reduced data requirement for training. Future research avenues could explore dynamic modeling of the redundant robot arm using SVR fused with fuzzy logic, while optimizing SVR performance through kernel parameter and regularization constant optimization.

Kar & Behera (2009) address the challenge of developing a visual motor control system for a 7 DOF robot manipulator. Their study utilizes a fuzzy self-organizing map (SOM) network to learn inverse kinematics and handle joint space redundancy. Techniques include fuzzy C-mean clustering for input space discretization, multi-step incremental learning for parameter updates, and sub-clustering in configuration space to manage complexity. Results show that the fuzzy SOM network achieves high positioning accuracy, conservative inverse kinematic solutions, and robust performance despite noise and calibration errors. Future enhancements may involve incorporating orientation feedback, obstacle and singularity avoidance, and comparative analyses with alternative methodologies.

III. METHODOLOGY

Kinematics Analysis of 7DOF Robot Arm

The Kinematics analysis computation is critical for identifying how robots move in a work environment. In 1981, Richard Paul demonstrated the usefulness of kinematic analysis in the context of robotic systems [12]. The Denavit-Hartenberg method was introduced by Jacques Denavit and Richard S. Hartenberg, which offers a systematic approach for defining the relationship between distinct coordinate frames that are connected to each joint of a robotic manipulator [12]. This model streamlines the study of robot motion by defining a uniform set of characteristics to describe the shape and position of each component and connection.

The LBR iiwa 7 R800, manufactured by KUKA AG, is a typical example of a robotic manipulator that has seven degrees of freedom and comprises exclusively of rotating

joints. This indicates that the manipulator is equipped with a 7R redundant configuration. The redundant manipulator, shown in Fig 1, consists of 7 interconnected frames that are linked to the links.

A. Fig 1: Defining coordinate systems for the Kuka LBR iiwa 7 R800.

It can be characterized as a kinematic chain consisting of n joints and $n-1$ links. Every joint in this sequence is equipped with a coordinate system (x, y, z) to determine its spatial orientation. These coordinate systems are adjustable via rotations and translations, allowing for perfect alignment between adjacent joints. Consequently, a homogeneous transformation matrix can be employed to depict each joint, specifying the precise rotation or translation needed to align the preceding joint with the subsequent one. This matrix generally incorporates both rotation and translation operations. The multiplication of these matrices determines the final position of the n th joint, which serves as the end effector of the robotic manipulator.

Fig 2: Representation of Denavit-Hartenberg parameters

Each joint of the manipulator robot is allocated a Cartesian coordinate system according to specific rules. The z_{k-1} axis aligns with the axis of rotation (rotation or translation) of joint k , the x_k axis is perpendicular to z_{k-1} and points towards the z_k axis, and the y_k axis completes an orthogonal system obeying the right-hand rule.

Furthermore, the parameters a_k , d_k , α_k , and θ_k describe the location and orientation of each joint. These parameters reflect the distances along the x_k and z_{k-1} axes, as well as the degrees of rotation around these axes, ensuring precise positioning and motion control of the robotic manipulator.

Table 1:

D-H parameters of 7-DoF redundant manipulator. (Ricardo X. et al. 2021)

i	α_i (rad)	a_i (mm)	d_i (mm)	θ_i (rad)
1	$-\frac{\pi}{2}$	0	$d_1 = 380$	θ_1
2	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	0	0	θ_2
3	$-\frac{\pi}{2}$	0	$d_3 = 328$	θ_3
4	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	0	0	θ_4
5	$-\frac{\pi}{2}$	0	$d_5 = 323$	θ_5
6	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	0	0	θ_6
7	0	0	$d_7 = 80$	θ_7

Note; a_i is the link length between the origin of successive frames ($i-1$ and i) along the x_i direction.

- a_i is the angle from z_{i-1} to z_i around x_i .
- d_i is the distance from x_{i-1} to x_i along the z_{i-1} direction.
- θ_i is the angle from x_{i-1} to x_i around z_{i-1} .

The Denavit-Hartenberg representation involves the multiplication of four fundamental transformations, consisting of rotations (R) and translations (Tr), as shown in the equation below.

Note, that $s_{\theta k}$ represents $\sin(\theta k)$ same as $c_{\theta k}$ for $\cos(\theta k)$:

$${}^{k-1}A_k = R_{z_k, \theta_k} \cdot Tr_{z_k, d_k} \cdot Tr_{x_k, a_k} \cdot R_{x_k, \alpha_k} =$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} c\theta k & -s\theta k & 0 & 0 \\ s\theta k & c\theta k & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & d_k \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c\alpha k & -s\alpha k & 0 \\ 0 & s\alpha k & c\alpha k & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note; that R_{z_k, θ_k} represents the rotation θ_k around the z_k axis, Tr_{z_k, d_k} represent the translation d_k along the z_k axis. Tr_{x_k, a_k} represents the translation a_k along the x_k , and R_{x_k, α_k} represents the rotational of α_k around the x_k axis.

The technique produces the matrix shown below, which provides the mapping of coordinates between two corresponding manipulator links of the robot:

$${}^{k-1}A_k = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_k & -s\theta_k & 0 & 0 \\ s\theta_k & c\theta_k & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note; the rotational joints, the joint variable is the angle θ_k , whereas the joint variable is the distance between the links d_k if it is prismatic. These parameters were obtained following the approach outlined by Denavit and Hartenberg.

Multiplying the transformation matrices generated by the Denavit–Hartenberg approach from $k = 0$ to n , generates the homogeneous transformation matrix from the base to the end effector. This resultant matrix serves as the answer to the forward kinematics problem for a manipulator with n degrees of freedom.

$$T = A_0n = A_{01} . A_{12} . A_{23} . \dots . A_{(n-1)n} = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_k & -s\theta_k & 0 & 0 \\ s\theta_k & c\theta_k & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note; that each matrix A_{ij} is a Denavit–Hartenberg Matrix define in Matrix (2).

The Homogenous Transformation Matrix solution of the 7DOF redundant manipulator forward kinematics problem:

$$T = A_0n = A_{01} . A_{12} . A_{23} . A_{34} . A_{45} . A_{56} . A_{67} = \begin{bmatrix} nx & ox & ax & x \\ ny & oy & ay & y \\ nz & oz & az & z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

following parameters; all joint configurations to position and orient the end effector on a given point in space, using following joint values, $\theta = [(\pi/6), (\pi/4), \pi, \pi, (\pi/3), -(\pi/3)]$ radians, and the non-zero parameters, $d_1 = 380$, $d_3 = 328$, $d_5 = 323$, and $d_7 = 80$.

The Inverse Kinematics Solution of The Manipulator Inverse Kinematic

The process of determining the joint angles necessary to precisely position the end-effector in three-dimensional space constitutes inverse kinematics for a 7-degree-of-freedom (7DOF) robotic arm. This complex task considers the arm's geometry, constraints, and desired end-effector position.

1. Dataset Generation and Preprocessing:

Generating a dataset on forward kinematics equations follow these steps:

- i. Define DH Parameters: Define the Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) parameters including alpha, a, d,

and theta. These parameters describe the geometric configuration of the robot's links and joints.

- ii. Create DH Parameter Table: Use the DH parameters to create a table displaying the parameters for each joint. This table helps in visualizing the robot's kinematic structure.
- iii. Implement Forward Kinematics: Implement the forward kinematics function using the DH parameters. This function computes the end-effector position based on the joint angles provided as input.
- iv. Generate Joint Angles: Define a range of joint angles to generate a dataset. These joint angles represent different configurations of the robot's joints.
- v. Compute End-Effector Positions: For each set of joint angles, compute the corresponding end-effector position using the forward kinematics function.
- vi. Define Target End-Effector Position: Define a target end-effector position that the robot needs to reach.
- vii. Define Optimization Parameters: Define parameters such as the number of generations, population size, mutation rate, and tolerance for the optimization algorithm.
- viii. Define Objective Function: Define an objective function that evaluates the distance between the computed end-effector position and the target position. This function guides the optimization process to find joint angles that minimize the distance.
- ix. Optimization Process: Use an optimization algorithm (e.g., genetic algorithm) to find the joint angles that minimize the distance between the computed end-effector position and the target position.
- x. Generate Dataset: Finally, generate a dataset containing the joint angles and corresponding end-effector positions. This dataset can be used for training and testing robotic systems.

2. Optimization Algorithms

The purpose of this comparison study is to find and choose the Optimization Algorithms for evaluation. These methods include Simulated Annealing, Differential Evolution, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Gradient Descent (Minimization) and Genetic Algorithm.

i. Simulated Annealing

Simulated Annealing (SA) exploits a similarity between the method in which a metal cools and freezes into a minimum energy crystalline form and the search for a minimum in a more general system.

It is a probabilistic search technique capable of discovering the global minimum amid multiple local minima, especially in a situation when previous approaches fail.

Max S. et al. (2008) propose Simulated Annealing, a probabilistic algorithm, to address inverse kinematics

challenges in robotics. Effective for complex applications, it reduces computing time and energy consumption by actuators compared to traditional methods. Their study underscores its potential for enhancing robotics performance and suggests further exploration for industrial applications.

Mathematically, Simulated Annealing iteratively adjusts the solution 'x' based on the objective function f(x) and a temperature parameter 'T' that influences the chance of accepting impoverished answers. The chance of adopting an impoverished option is determined by the Metropolis criterion:

$$P(\Delta E) = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E}{k_B T}\right)$$

Where ΔE is the change in energy (or cost function), k_B is Boltzmann's constant, and T is the current temperature. As the algorithm progresses, T decreases, leading to a more deterministic search.

The steps involved in using simulated annealing for inverse kinematic solution:

1. Define objective function: Measure error between desired and calculated end-effector positions, returning scalar.
2. Initialize joint angles (theta1 to theta7) with random or prior knowledge-based guesses.
3. Set up Simulated Annealing: • Define initial (T_max) and final (T_min) temperatures. • Choose parameters for cooling schedule and acceptance probability.
4. Conduct Simulated Annealing Optimization: • Initialize algorithm with objective function, guesses, and parameters. • Run until convergence or stopping criterion. • Retrieve best joint angles (best_thetas) and error (best_error). • Optionally, track best solutions history (best_history).
5. View Results: • Display best joint angles (best_thetas) and error (best_error). • Optionally, plot optimization history.

ii. Differential Evolution

Differential Evolution (DE) is a population-based optimization algorithm that can handle nonlinear and multimodal optimization problems. The mutation operation in Differential Evolution (DE) uses the vector differences between the current population members to determine the magnitude and direction of the perturbation given to each individual throughout the mutation process.

Enrique R. et al. (2016) employ Differential Evolution (DE) to address robot inverse kinematics for a four Degrees of Freedom (DOF) robot. Their multi-objective DE method minimizes positional inaccuracy and angular displacement, outperforming conventional DE, Genetic Algorithm (GA), and Algebraic Method (AM) in achieving better results for joint rotation limits.

Mathematically, this process is represented as:

Differential Evolution (DE) is for generating the trial solution through mutation and crossover operations. The trial solution u_i for the i -th candidate in the population is computed as follows:

$$u_i = x_{i1} + F \cdot (x_{i2} - x_{i3})$$

where:

- u_i is the trial solution being generated.
- x_{i1} , x_{i2} , and x_{i3} are three distinct candidate solutions randomly selected from the current population.
- F is the scaling factor, which controls the amplification of the difference vector ($x_{i2} - x_{i3}$).

The final equation for generating the trial solution with crossover is often represented as:

$$v_{ij} = \begin{cases} u_{ij}, & \text{if } \text{rand}(0,1) \leq CR \text{ or } j = j_r \\ x_{ij}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where:

- v_{ij} is the j -th component of the trial solution.
- u_{ij} is the j -th component of the mutated solution.
- x_{ij} is the j -th component of the original candidate solution.
- $\text{rand}(0,1)$ generates a random number between 0 and 1.
- j_r is a randomly selected index indicating which component of the trial solution is always included.

Below are the steps involved in utilizing differential evolution for inverse kinematic solutions:

1. Define objective function (objective_function) to compute error between desired and achieved end-effector poses.
2. Initialize parameters: num_joints, population_size, num_generations, mutation_rate, LB, and UB for joint angles.
3. Create DE algorithm instance (da) with objective function, dimensions (equal to num_joints), population size, generations, mutation rate, and joint angle bounds.
4. Execute DE algorithm: Call run() method of da to evolve population over generations, minimizing objective function.
5. Get results: Retrieve best solution with joint angles (best_thetas) minimizing error (best_error). Also, collect best solutions history (best_history).
6. Output: Return best_thetas, best_error, and best_history from differential_evolution() function.
7. Display results: Print best joint angles and error. Optionally, plot best solutions evolution using plot_best_history().

iii. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)

PSO is inspired by the social behaviour of bird flocks and fish schools, iteratively updates particles' positions in a

multidimensional space to find optimal solutions. It's a computational method that enhances candidate solutions iteratively to optimize a problem. By moving particles based on mathematical formulas, influenced by local and global best positions, PSO navigates the search space toward optimal solutions, leveraging the collective intelligence of the swarm to make better choices.

Mathematically, each particle's position (x_i) and velocity (v_i) are updated using the following equations:

Velocity Update :

$$v_i(t + 1) = w \cdot v_i(t) + c_1 \cdot \text{rand}_1 \cdot (p_{\text{best}} - x_i(t)) + c_2 \cdot \text{rand}_2 \cdot (g_{\text{best}} - x_i(t))$$

Position Update :

$$x_i(t + 1) = x_i(t) + v_i(t + 1)$$

Where :

- w is the inertia weight,
- c_1 and c_2 are acceleration coefficients,
- rand_1 and rand_2 are random numbers between 0 and 1,
- p_{best} is the best-known position of the particle,
- g_{best} is the best-known position of the entire swarm,
- $v_i(t)$ is the velocity of particle i at time t ,
- $x_i(t)$ is the position of particle i at time t ,
- $v_i(t + 1)$ is the updated velocity of particle i at time $t+1$, and
- $x_i(t + 1)$ is the updated position of particle i at time $t+1$.

Here are the steps involved in implementing the inverse kinematic solution using PSO:

1. Define objective function: Measure error between desired and actual end-effector positions.
2. Initialize PSO Algorithm: • Set parameters: dimensions (number of joints), population size, iterations (generations), angle bounds, inertia weight (w), cognitive factor (c_1), and social factor (c_2). • Initiate PSO algorithm with these parameters and the defined objective function.
3. Execute PSO Optimization: Call `run()` method to optimize joint angles, minimizing position error.
4. Get Results: • Retrieve best joint angles (`best_thetas`), corresponding error (`best_error`), and history of best error values (`best_history`).
5. Output Results: • Print or visualize best joint angles (`best_thetas`) using `print_thetas()`. • Print corresponding error (`best_error`). • Plot history of best error values (`best_history`) for convergence observation.
6. Optional Post-Processing: • Additional steps like converting angles to commands or further optimization for desired accuracy may be needed.

iv. Genetic Algorithm (GA)

A genetic algorithm (GA), acts as a search approach within computers, aiming at identifying real or approximate answers for optimization and search difficulties. Categorized as global search heuristics, genetic algorithms belong to a particular type of evolutionary algorithms. They take influence from evolutionary biology, including mechanisms like inheritance, mutation, selection, and crossover, also known as recombination.

GA operates on a population of chromosomes, each representing a potential solution x . Selection mechanisms like tournament or roulette wheel favor individuals with higher fitness for reproduction. Crossover and mutation operations foster genetic diversity, aiding solution space exploration. The mathematical expressions for the GA are as follows:

$$\text{Fitness} = f(x)$$

$$P(\text{selection}) = \frac{\text{Fitness}}{\sum \text{Fitness}}$$

To solve inverse kinematics using a genetic algorithm, you can follow these steps:

1. Define Objective Function: Create function evaluating joint angle set's performance, measuring proximity to desired end-effector position.
2. Initialization: Set genetic algorithm parameters - generations, population size, mutation rate. Also, define joint angle bounds.
3. Initialize Population: Generate initial joint angle configurations randomly within bounds.
4. Evaluation: Assess each individual's fitness using objective function.
5. Selection: Pick individuals based on fitness; better fitness increases chance of reproduction.
6. Crossover: Combine genetic information of selected individuals to create offspring.
7. Mutation: Introduce diversity by randomly changing genes (joint angles) of selected individuals.
8. Replacement: Replace least fit individuals with new offspring.
9. Termination: Repeat steps 4-8 for specified generations or until termination criterion met.

v. Gradient Descent (Minimization)

Gradient Descent (GD) is a first-order optimization algorithm that iteratively updates the parameters of a model in the direction of the steepest descent of the objective function. It is commonly used in machine learning and optimization tasks, including parameter estimation, optimization of neural network weights, and optimization-based control in robotics.

Mathematically, this process is represented as:

$$q_{\text{new}} = q_{\text{current}} - \alpha \nabla C(q_{\text{current}})$$

Where (q_{new}) is the updated joint configuration, $q_{current}$ is the current joint configuration, α is the learning rate controlling the step size, and $\nabla C(q_{current})$ is the gradient of the cost function C with respect to the joint configurations.

Below are the steps involved in implementing inverse kinematics using gradient descent minimization techniques:

1. Define Objective Function: Create function measuring error between desired and achieved robot pose. It computes the difference given joint angles.
2. Initialization: Set initial guess for joint angles (thetas) to zeros array.
3. Set Bounds: Specify joint angle bounds as (min, max) values for each angle.
4. Minimization: Use optimization algorithm (e.g., gradient descent) to minimize objective function.
5. Optimization Result: Extract optimized thetas and error from result.
6. Return Results: Return optimized thetas and error.
7. Print Results: Display optimized thetas and error for analysis.

3. Machine Learning

Machine learning is a subset of artificial intelligence where algorithms and statistical models are utilized to enable machines to learn from data, identify patterns, and make decisions, with the objective of simulating human-like cognitive processes and enhancing accuracy over time.

Below are the steps on how the data was generated:

1. Number of Samples: It generates a large number of samples ($n_{samples} = 100000$) to represent different configurations of the robotic arm.
2. Joint Angle Ranges: It defines permissible ranges for each joint angle in radians. These ranges specify the limits within which each joint angle can vary.
3. Random Joint Angles: It generates random joint angles within their respective ranges using `np.random.uniform()` function. This creates random configurations of the robotic arm.
4. Forward Kinematics: It computes the end-effector positions corresponding to each set of joint angles using a forward kinematics function called `forward_kinematics()`. This function calculates the position of the end-effector based on the joint angles provided.
5. DataFrame Creation: It creates a Pandas DataFrame to organize the generated data. The DataFrame has columns for each joint angle (`theta1` to `theta7`) and the corresponding x , y , and z coordinates of the end-effector position.
6. Display or Save Data: Optionally, it can display the first 10 rows of the DataFrame or save the entire dataset to a CSV file.

i. Neural Network

Neural networks are built of node layers, containing an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Each node, or artificial neuron is connected to another and has an corresponding weight and threshold. If the output of any particular node is above the given threshold value, that node is activated, transmitting data to the next level of the network.

Wagaa et al. (2023) investigate inverse kinematics challenges in high degrees of freedom robotic arms, exploring analytical and deep learning methods. Their findings underscore the Bidirectional Long–Short Term Memory network's superior performance in accurately determining joint variables for precise end-effector placement.

Architecture and working of Neural Networks

To comprehend the structure of a neural network, it's essential to delve into the functionality of a neuron initially.

Fig 3: An Artificial Neuron

Every input received by an artificial neuron is assigned a weight. These inputs are then multiplied by their corresponding weights, and the result is added to a bias, forming what is known as the weighted sum. This weighted sum subsequently undergoes an activation function, typically a non-linear function. An artificial neuron can be likened to a linear regression model, either simple or multiple, with an activation function applied at the conclusion.

Fig 4: Neural Network

A neural network typically comprises multiple layers, with each layer containing numerous neurons interconnected to those in the subsequent layers. In Figure 4, a network with

four layers is depicted. The initial layer, termed the input layer, appears to encompass six neurons, representing the input data's dimensions. The ultimate layer serves as the output layer, its neuron count predetermined by the dataset's characteristics and the problem type. The hidden layers' neuron count and quantity are determined through iterative experimentation.

Neurons within layer i receive outputs from all neurons in the preceding layer ($i-1$), calculate a weighted sum, incorporate a bias, and then apply an activation function. This process mirrors that of an artificial neuron. Neurons in each hidden layer are fully connected to those in the preceding layer. For instance, neurons in the first hidden layer receive inputs from all neurons in the input layer. Subsequently, neurons in subsequent hidden layers receive inputs from the previous hidden layer's neurons.

A layer comprising m neurons following a layer with n neurons entails $(n * m) + m$ connections, including biases. These connections possess weights initialized randomly, which are optimized during training to minimize the chosen loss function.

Below are the steps involved in implementing inverse kinematics using Neural Network:

1. Import Libraries: Use NumPy, pandas, scikit-learn for data and TensorFlow for neural networks.
2. Prepare Data: Preprocess data, split into train-test sets with train-test split.
3. Define NN Architecture: Design network layers, neurons, and activation functions with Keras Sequential API.
4. Compile Model: Use compile method to specify optimizer, loss function, and evaluation metrics.
5. Train Model: Fit compiled model with training data, epochs, batch size, and optional validation split.
6. Evaluate Model: Assess model performance on test data with evaluate method, calculating loss and accuracy.
7. Calculate Metrics: Optionally compute additional metrics like MSE, RMSE, MAE, and R^2 using scikit-learn.
8. Print Results: Display evaluation results for model performance analysis.

ii. Linear Regression Model

Linear regression is a fundamental supervised learning technique in machine learning used to model the relationship between a dependent variable (target) and one or more independent variables (predictors) by fitting a linear equation to observed data. It's primarily used for predictive analysis and modeling the relationship between variables.

For a simple linear regression model, there's only one independent variable, x , and one dependent variable, y . The relationship between them is modeled as:

$$y = mx + b$$

Where:

- y is the dependent variable (the variable being predicted),
- x is the independent variable (the variable used for prediction),
- m is the slope of the line (the coefficient that represents the effect of x on y),
- b is the y-intercept (the value of y when x is 0).

To find the values of m and b that minimize the error, we can use the Ordinary Least Squares method. The formulas for m and b in terms of the data points are:

$$m = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$

$$b = \bar{y} - m\bar{x}$$

Below are the steps involved in implementing inverse kinematics using Linear regression:

1. Splitting the Dataset: Divide the dataset into features (X) and target variables (y).
2. Splitting into Training and Testing Sets: Split the data into training and testing sets. This is crucial for evaluating the model's performance.
3. Feature Scaling: Scale the features to ensure they are on a similar scale. This step is important for many machine learning algorithms to converge effectively.
4. Polynomial Features (Optional): If necessary, create polynomial features from the original features. This can help capture nonlinear relationships between the features and the target variable.
5. Train the Linear Regression Model: Create an instance of the LinearRegression model and train it using the training data.
6. Make Predictions: Use the trained model to make predictions on the testing data.
7. Compute Evaluation Metrics: Calculate evaluation metrics such as mean squared error (MSE) and R-squared score to assess the performance of the model on both the training and testing sets.
8. Access Model Parameters: Access the coefficients and intercept of the trained linear regression model.

iii. Decision Tree

Decision Tree is a Supervised learning technique for classification and Regression problems, primarily used for Classification. It's a tree classifier where internal nodes represent dataset features, branches denote decision rules, and leaf nodes signify outcomes. It's a graphical representation providing all possible solutions based on

conditions, resembling a tree with a root node branching out to construct a tree-like structure.

Below are the steps involved in implementing inverse kinematics using Decision Tree:

- i. Import Libraries: Import the necessary libraries, including DecisionTreeRegressor from sklearn.tree and mean_squared_error from sklearn.metrics.
- ii. Initialize the Model: Initialize the Decision Tree Regressor with specific parameters, such as max_depth=3 and random_state=42.
- iii. Model Training: Fit the initialized Decision Tree Regressor (tree_model) with the training data (X_train_poly, y_train)
- iv. Prediction: Predict the target variable (y_pred_tree) using the trained model on the test data (X_test_poly).
- v. Calculate Mean Squared Error (MSE): Calculate the Mean Squared Error (mse_dt) between the predicted values (y_pred_tree) and the actual target values (y_test).
- vi. Visualize Decision Tree: Visualize the trained decision tree using plot_tree from sklearn.tree and matplotlib.pyplot. This involves plotting the decision tree structure, potentially with node colors indicating class probabilities and feature names as labels.
- vii. Display Mean Squared Error (MSE): Print the Mean Squared Error (mse_dt) obtained from the model evaluation.
- viii. Evaluate R² Score: Calculate the R-squared (r2) score using r2_score from sklearn.metrics between the predicted values (tree_model.predict(X_test_poly)) and the actual target values (y_test). Then, print the R-squared score. Adjust the parameters of r2_score as needed based on the specific requirements of your analysis.

iv. Support Vector Machine

A support vector machine (SVM) is a supervised learning algorithm used for solving complex classification, regression, and outlier detection tasks. It determines boundaries between data points based on predefined classes or labels by performing optimal data transformations. SVMs locate an optimal hyperplane in a high-dimensional space, serving as a decision boundary that effectively separates data points of different classes

The mathematical expressions for the SVM are as follows:

$$W \cdot X_i + b \geq 1, \forall X_i, \text{ with } y_i = 1$$

$$W \cdot X_i + b \leq -1, \forall X_i, \text{ with } y_i = -1$$

$$\text{as, } y_i (W \cdot X_i + b) \geq 1, \forall X_i$$

Below are the steps involved in implementing inverse kinematics using SVM:

1. Define the Model: Create a pipeline for the SVM model using make_pipeline. In the pipeline, include

preprocessing steps such as polynomial feature generation, standardization, and use MultiOutputRegressor with SVR as the base estimator.

2. Train the Model: Fit the training data to the SVM model using the fit method.
3. Make Predictions: Use the trained model to make predictions on both the training and testing datasets using the predict method.
4. Evaluate the Model: Calculate evaluation metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE) and R-squared (R²) using the mean_squared_error and r2_score functions from sklearn's metrics module.
5. Print Results: Print the calculated MSE and R² for both the training and testing sets to evaluate the performance of the SVM model.

IV. RESULTS

- a. Comparison of the obtained results:

The data collected from the optimisation algorithm studies examined in this research are presented.

Table 2:

Solution Name	θ1	θ2	θ3	θ4	θ5	θ6	θ7	x	y	z	Error	Diff
GD	-1.08746	-0.907833	-0.0940555	0.00962785	-0.000497597	-0.0122602	0	-267.17	508.444	832.163	0.00123675	0.00123675
DE	2.10464	0.879814	1.3247	0.000848759	-0.676234	0.00397089	0.996431	-287.204	484.859	845.602	0.00123668	0.00123668
PSO	2.09016	0.883546	-0.957877	-1.28758e-06	2.21756	2.69867e-06	0.607073	-280.456	490.546	843.757	0.00123667	0.00123667
SA	2.5206	0.806125	-3.14159	-0.220634	-3.14159	-0.649508	-2.36733	-441.236	315.664	848.632	0.00126461	0.00126461
GA	-0.883338	0.827386	1.05404	0.0513751	-1.86853	-0.159008	2.41004	-319.045	431.367	874.678	0.00123915	0.00123915

The report emphasizes the significance of the error value in utilizing optimization algorithms for solving Inverse Kinematics. This value quantifies the variance between the intended and realized positions of the robotic arm's end-effector. Specifically, the error is determined by comparing the desired and actual positions of the end-effector when reaching a predefined target or executing a particular task. It serves as a quantitative gauge of the effectiveness of the optimized joint angles in attaining the desired configuration or motion of the robotic arm.

After evaluating the result from Table 2 of optimization algorithms, the best among the algorithm was Particle swarm optimization (PSO) with a low error value of 0.00123667, indicates that the optimized joint angles result in a robotic arm configuration that closely matches the desired configuration or achieves the desired task with high accuracy.

The data collected from the AI algorithm studies examined in this research are presented.

Table 3:

Model	Mean Squared Error (MSE)	R-squared (R ²)
Linear Regression	1.15242	0.0181475
Decision Tree	1.15227	0.0182817
Neural Network	1.31499	-0.172849

Support Vector Machine	42542.5	0.606929
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R-squared (R^2) or Coefficient of Determination:

- R^2 is a statistical measure that represents the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables.
- It indicates the goodness of fit of the model to the data.
- R^2 value ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates a perfect fit and 0 indicates no linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

The formula for R^2 is:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{res}}{SS_{total}}$$

Where:

- SS_{res} is the sum of squared residuals (errors) from the regression model,
- SS_{total} is the total sum of squares from the mean of the dependent variable.

Mean Square Error (MSE): It is the average of the error squares between prediction and actual values.

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

Where:

- n is the number of samples,
- y_i is the actual value for the i_{th} sample,
- \hat{y}_i is the predicted value for the i_{th} sample.

After evaluating the result from Table 3 of Machine Learning algorithms, the Decision Tree algorithm appears to be the best machine learning algorithm for this particular task. Here's the reasoning:

1. **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** The Decision Tree algorithm has the lowest MSE of 1.15227 among all the models. A lower MSE indicates that the model's predictions are closer to the actual values, suggesting better overall performance in terms of prediction accuracy.
2. **R-squared (R^2):** The Decision Tree algorithm also has the highest R-squared value of 0.0182817. While R-squared alone should not be used as the sole criterion for model selection, it indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables. A higher R-squared value suggests that the model explains more of the variance in the data, which is desirable.

Therefore, based on both the MSE and R-squared metrics, the Decision Tree algorithm seems to outperform the other models in terms of predictive accuracy and explanatory power.

- b. Comparing the Optimization algorithm and the AI algorithm

Overall Comparison:

Both PSO and the Decision Tree algorithm demonstrated strengths in their respective domains:

- PSO excelled in optimizing complex systems like robotic arms, providing accurate solutions with minimal error.
- The Decision Tree algorithm showcased superior predictive accuracy and explanatory power, making it an excellent choice for tasks requiring machine learning-based predictions.

Considerations for Application:

Depending on the specific requirements of the task:

- If the primary goal is to optimize parameters for a complex system like a robotic arm, PSO would be the preferred choice due to its ability to find near-optimal solutions efficiently.
- For tasks involving prediction and classification, especially where interpretability is important, the Decision Tree algorithm would be more suitable, given its strong performance in predictive accuracy and explanatory power.

In conclusion, while both PSO and the Decision Tree algorithm excel in different domains, the choice between them should be based on the specific requirements and objectives of the task at hand.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this report offers a thorough comparative examination of optimization algorithms and AI models for addressing Inverse Kinematics in a 7-DOF robotic setup. The assessment concentrated on appraising these approaches' efficacy through error metrics like Mean Squared Error (MSE) and R-squared (R^2). Results revealed that Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) produced the most minimal error, signifying precise joint angle optimization for the robotic arm. Conversely, AI models, notably the Decision Tree algorithm, displayed promising predictive capabilities for the robotic arm's configurations, exhibiting low MSE and relatively high R^2 values compared to alternatives such as Linear Regression, Neural Network, and Support Vector Machine. Future endeavors could focus on refining optimization algorithms to further reduce error values and enhance joint angle optimization efficiency. Exploring advanced AI models or their combination for improved predictive accuracy holds potential for research. Moreover, real-time implementation and testing of these algorithms and models on physical robotic systems would offer valuable insights into their practicality and performance in real-world scenarios. Ultimately, this comparative analysis lays a robust groundwork for future research endeavors to advance robotic kinematics and optimization techniques.

VI. REFERENCES

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Appendices

- Link to the code:
https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1-6eIctbV_hrHCY7H6advSuNC8mRwwXD2?usp=sharing
- Link to the dataset:
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1rkl_8ZdygbmsAvINzrFmpq0Dv78G46SP/view?usp=sharing